

TAX SOVEREIGNTY IN LEBANESE LAW: FATCA AND DIGITAL ECONOMY CHALLENGES.

RAFIK OREH WALID GHRAIZI

ISLAMIC UNIVERSITY of LEBANON (IUL)

Faculty of Law – Department of Graduate Studies (Ph.D.)

2025

The Author Declares No Conflict of Interest.

This Research Received No Specific Grant from Any Funding
Agency in the Public, Commercial, or Not-For-Profit Sectors.

ABSTRACT

Purpose: This study examines how developing countries navigate the tension between international tax compliance and fiscal sovereignty, using Lebanon as a representative case study. It investigates the impact of two critical frameworks: the United States Foreign Account Tax Compliance Act (FATCA) and taxation of digital economy giants (GAFA), and their implications for territorial tax systems in small developing states.

Design/Methodology/Approach: The study employs doctrinal legal analysis, examining Lebanese tax legislation, particularly Legislative Decree No. 144 of 1959, alongside international tax compliance requirements. Lebanon serves as an illustrative case demonstrating challenges common to developing countries with territorial tax systems facing extraterritorial enforcement mechanisms. The research analyzes legal mechanisms through which foreign tax authorities exercise extraterritorial jurisdiction and their implications for national sovereignty.

Findings: The research reveals that developing countries adopting territorial tax principles face fundamental conflicts with powerful states' worldwide taxation policies enforced through FATCA. Financial institutions in these countries face compliance obligations that effectively subordinate national tax interests to foreign revenue collection. Similarly, digital economy taxation presents universal challenges as cross-border electronic commerce transcends geographical tax jurisdictions. The Lebanese experience demonstrates patterns common to small developing states lacking capacity to resist fiscal imperialism or effectively tax deterritorialized digital commerce.

Practical Implications: The findings demonstrate that developing nations must balance compliance with powerful foreign tax regimes against erosion of fiscal sovereignty. The study identifies specific legal and operational challenges facing financial institutions in implementing foreign tax reporting requirements, with implications extending beyond Lebanon to similar jurisdictions worldwide.

Originality/Value: This paper provides comprehensive analysis of FATCA and GAFA impacts on developing country tax sovereignty, contributing to scholarship on fiscal imperialism and challenges facing small states in maintaining fiscal autonomy in an increasingly digitized global economy. While focused on Lebanese law as a case study, the findings have significant transferability to other developing countries facing similar pressures.

Keywords: Tax Sovereignty, FATCA, GAFA, Digital Economy Taxation, Territorial Tax System, International Tax Compliance, Developing Countries, Lebanese Tax Law

Article Classification: Research Paper

TABLE OF CONTENTS

1. Introduction.....	3
2. Conceptual Framework Tax Sovereignty and tax Systems.....	4
2.1 Defining Tax Sovereignty	4
2.2 Global Tax Systems: Source versus Residence.....	5
2.3 Lebanon's Territorial Tax System.....	6
3. FATCA: American Extraterritorial Tax Enforcement	11
3.1 Legislative Background and Objectives	12
3.2 FATCA's Operational Mechanism	12
3.3 Implementation Models	14
3.4 FATCA's Impact on Lebanese Sovereignty	17
3.5 FATCA as Tax Imperialism.....	18
4. Digital Economy Taxation: The Gafa Challenge	20
4.1 The Digital Economy and Tax Sovereignty	20
4.2 Lebanon's Digital Economy Tax Gap	21
4.3 The GAFA Tax Response.....	23
4.4 Challenges and Criticisms.....	24
5. Comparative Analysis: Sovereignty Under Pressure	28
5.1 Asymmetric Power Relations.....	28
6. Conclusion And Policy Recommendations.....	30
6.1 Key Findings.....	30
6.2 Policy Recommendations for Lebanon.....	31
6.3 Theoretical Implications	32
6.4 Future Research Directions.....	32
7. References.....	34

1. INTRODUCTION

Every state possesses sovereignty over its territory, traditionally understood as control over land, sea, and air borders, maintenance of public security, and extension of state authority throughout its territory. However, sovereignty extends beyond these physical dimensions to encompass fiscal autonomy—the state's exclusive right to tax activities within its authority without external interference or compulsory revenue sharing with foreign governments.

Contemporary developments in international finance and digital commerce have fundamentally challenged traditional concepts of tax sovereignty for developing countries. Two phenomena exemplify this challenge: first, the extraterritorial reach of the United States Foreign Account Tax Compliance Act (FATCA), which compels global financial institutions to serve as agents of American tax enforcement; second, the emergence of digital commerce taxation debates surrounding multinational technology corporations, commonly known as GAFAs (Google, Apple, Facebook, Amazon) taxation.

This study examines these challenges through detailed analysis of Lebanese tax law, which serves as a representative case of how small developing countries with territorial tax systems navigate the tension between international compliance demands and fiscal sovereignty. Lebanon's tax system, codified primarily in Legislative Decree No. 144 of 1959, taxes income generated within its borders regardless of the taxpayer's nationality or residence. This territorial approach, common among developing nations, contrasts sharply with citizenship-based taxation systems, particularly that of the United States, creating inherent jurisdictional conflicts.

The selection of Lebanon as the primary case study is justified on several grounds. First, Lebanon exemplifies small developing states with limited capacity to resist external fiscal pressures. Second, its territorial tax system represents a common approach among developing countries. Third, its experience with FATCA compliance and digital economy challenges demonstrates patterns applicable to similar authorities. Fourth, comprehensive documentation of Lebanese legislative responses and banking sector adaptations provides rich empirical material for analysis.

The research addresses two central questions with implications extending beyond Lebanon: First, how does FATCA compliance affect developing countries' ability to exercise sovereign tax

authority over income generated within their territories? Second, what challenges does digital economy taxation present to territorial tax frameworks in developing countries, and how do international responses like GAFAs taxation reflect evolving concepts of fiscal sovereignty?

By analyzing Lebanese legislative responses, banking sector compliance mechanisms, and international tax policy developments, this study illuminates tensions between national fiscal autonomy and global tax cooperation regimes affecting all developing countries. The findings contribute to broader debates about fiscal imperialism, the rights of developing nations in international tax governance, and the adaptation of territorial tax systems to digital economic realities.

While this research focuses primarily on Lebanese law, the analysis has significant implications for all developing countries facing similar pressures. The Lebanese experience provides insights transferable to other small states navigating the same dilemmas between compliance with powerful foreign tax regimes and preservation of fiscal sovereignty.

1. CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK: TAX SOVEREIGNTY AND TAX SYSTEMS

2.1 Defining Tax Sovereignty

Tax sovereignty constitutes a fundamental attribute of statehood, encompassing the exclusive authority to levy taxes on economic activities within territorial boundaries. This authority derives from the state's general sovereignty and represents both a manifestation of state power and an expression of social solidarity among citizens contributing to public goods (Saleh, 2006).

Lebanese jurisprudence characterizes taxation as a "compulsory and final obligation" that serves as an "expression of state sovereignty and a manifestation of social solidarity to achieve the public good" (Saleh, 2006, p. 51). Three essential characteristics define taxation under this framework:

First, taxes are compulsory, meaning imposed and collected by force of law without voluntary consent. Second, taxes are final, meaning they are not subject to negotiation or bargaining, nor to modification or withdrawal. Third, taxation represents an expression of state sovereignty.

Consequently, from these definitions, it can be concluded that tax imposition is a matter related to public order and cannot be agreed to violate it. Moreover, it is among the concepts greater than public order, as it is linked to sovereignty.

However, the principle of tax sovereignty may encounter obstacles related to the differences in tax systems around the world adopted by states. If all states adopted one system, such as imposing tax on profits realized within the territory, there would be no tax conflict and dispute. But the matter differs when a state adopts, for example, the criterion of nationality in imposing tax, while another state adopts the criterion of residence. Then a national of a certain state residing in another state would be subject to two taxes. Both taxes are sovereign with respect to the states imposing them, and neither will relinquish its tax.

Therefore, from here, we will subsequently examine the tax systems adopted around the world, particularly the territorial tax system common in developing countries and exemplified by Lebanon.

2.2 Global Tax Systems: Source versus Residence

International tax systems employ two principal theoretical foundations for asserting taxing jurisdiction: source-based taxation and residence-based taxation.

2.2.1 Source-Based Taxation

Source-based systems tax income based on where economic value is generated. Proponents argue that the source state provides the infrastructure, legal framework, and economic environment that enables wealth creation, thereby justifying its primary claim to tax revenues. This approach aligns with benefit theory—taxpayers should contribute to the jurisdiction that facilitates their income generation.

2.2.2 Residence-Based Taxation

Residence-based systems tax individuals and entities based on their domicile or place of incorporation, regardless of income source. This approach subdivides into two variants.

The first variant is worldwide taxation, where residents pay tax on global income to their country of residence. The United States exemplifies this approach, taxing citizens and residents on worldwide income regardless of where earned.

The second variant is territorial taxation, where residents pay tax only on domestically-sourced income. Foreign-earned income remains untaxed by the residence jurisdiction.

The tax system followed in any state follows one of the following two theories. The first theory is the source of income theory, or what is known as Source-Based Tax. The second theory is the residence theory, or what is known as Residence-Based Taxation. While the residence theory is divided into two branches: the first branch is the Worldwide Tax System, and the second branch is the Territorial Tax System.

Accordingly, proponents of the source theory base the right to claim and impose tax on the basis that the source state provided and generated the opportunity to generate income and profits, and therefore has the right and priority to impose taxes on them.

As for proponents of the residence theory, they rely on the fact that the state of residence provides the appropriate climate, services, ground, and economy to achieve profit, and therefore it is the duty of residents, both companies and individuals, to contribute to the revenues of the state that provides all the services that enable them to achieve profits.

Taxes may be imposed on income or profits resulting from international activities such as cross-border investment where income is obtained based on the source of the taxable activity (source country), or when the person receiving it is primarily a resident in the state (country of residence). Residence-based taxation relies on the principle that individuals and companies should contribute to the public services provided to them by the state in which they live, on all their income from any source. Source taxation is justified from the perspective that the state providing the opportunity to generate income, or profits should have the right to impose taxes on them.

2.3 Territorial Tax Systems in Developing Countries: The Lebanese Example

Many developing countries, including Lebanon, have adopted territorial tax systems as a practical approach to taxation that aligns with their administrative capacities and economic structures. Lebanon's system, codified in Article 3 of the Income Tax Law, provides a clear example of this approach: "Tax is imposed in the name of natural and legal persons, residing in Lebanese territory or abroad, on profits they realize in Lebanon" (Legislative Decree No. 144, 1959).

This territorial principle, common to many developing countries, establishes several key features. First, the determinative factor is where economic activity occurs, not taxpayer nationality or residence. Second, there is geographical limitation where only domestically sourced income faces taxation. Third, income earned abroad remains untaxed, even by residents. Fourth, there is non-discrimination where foreign entities earning domestic-source income face the same tax obligations as domestic entities.

2.3.1 Application to Employment Income

Lebanese tax law demonstrates territorial principles through wage and salary taxation, providing insights applicable to other territorial tax systems. Article 46 of the Income Tax Law distinguishes between public and private sector employment.

For the public sector, tax applies to all payments from Lebanese public funds regardless of where services are performed or the recipient's residence. Conversely, foreign public funds such as embassies and diplomatic missions generally receive reciprocal tax exemption for their employees, subject to bilateral reciprocity agreements.

For the private sector, tax applies when services are performed within Lebanese territory, regardless of the employer's location or the employee's residence. This creates clear nexus requirements—physical presence and activity within the country triggers tax liability.

The meaning of this principle is that income tax on profits realized by companies or individuals from activities practiced in the country is subject to domestic income tax, as well as profits subject to tax under a tax treaty.

Profit realized within the country is subject to domestic tax regardless of the company's nationality and regardless of the nationality of people subject to tax. From this standpoint, foreign companies are subject to domestic income tax law regarding profits they earn from their activities within the country, regardless of the nationality of these companies or their place of residence. Conversely, profits realized by agents, representatives, or branches of local companies from operations they conduct abroad are not subject to income tax.

As a result of this territorial character, companies cannot compensate for losses they incur abroad with profits they earn domestically, and vice versa.

One manifestation of the principle of tax territoriality is the tax on salaries and wages, according to Article 46 of the Income Tax Law, which stipulates that the tax covers salaries, wages, compensations, allowances, public and private retirement pensions, and lifetime allowances that accrue on Lebanese territory from a public fund, to every person residing in Lebanon or abroad, and from a private fund, to every person residing in Lebanon, as well as to every person residing abroad for services performed in Lebanon.

However, this text was unable to determine the scope of application of tax on salaries and wages, which necessitated the issuance of Circular No. 2541/S1 dated December 18, 2002 from the Minister of Finance, whereby the principles of applying the provisions of Article 46 of Legislative Decree No. 144 dated June 12, 1959 and its amendments (Income Tax Law) related to the territoriality of tax on salaries and wages were determined.

Under this circular, the place of tax imposition was determined for the public sector and the private sector.

For the public sector, the criterion of the place of tax imposition on salaries and wages was adopted based on the location of the public fund regardless of the place of service performance or the

beneficiary's place of residence. In this regard, a distinction was made between the Lebanese public fund represented by public sector funds or Lebanese public funds, meaning state, municipalities, and public institutions affiliated with the state or municipalities, and funds of other legal persons with public character.

Based on the foregoing, the circular based on the law imposed that all amounts paid from a Lebanese public fund are subject to tax whether the beneficiary resides in Lebanon or abroad, and whether the service was performed within Lebanese territory or in a foreign country.

As for the foreign public fund, it means funds of embassies, diplomatic missions, and international, Arab, and foreign organizations. These salaries and wages, according to the principle of tax territoriality, are subject to income tax on salaries and wages. However, the circular issued by the Minister of Finance mentioned above, as an exception to the principle of tax territoriality but with the condition of reciprocity, meaning that Lebanese diplomatic missions and embassies are exempted from tax on salaries and wages within these countries.

The circular also stipulated that salaries and wages are subject to tax in Lebanon when the beneficiary resides in it and for services performed within Lebanese territory, such as Lebanese or local employees present in Lebanon before contracting with them at foreign embassies.

This principle differs from what is applied to the private sector. In the private sector, the principle is that salaries and wages in Lebanon are subject to tax on amounts accruing to a private fund if the service was performed in Lebanon regardless of the beneficiary's place of residence whether on Lebanese territory or outside it.

Therefore, a distinction must be made between services performed in Lebanon and employees who are sent outside Lebanon but temporarily.

The principle states that tax is imposed on salaries and wages accruing on Lebanese territory to a private fund for services performed in Lebanon, regardless of the location of the debtor private fund or the place of residence of the beneficiary person, whether residing in Lebanon or not. Service is considered performed in Lebanon if the activity of the employed beneficiary of the wage is exerted in Lebanon.

As for employees sent abroad, in this case, if the activities are temporary for the benefit of the establishment, the salaries paid to them for these activities are subject to tax in Lebanon.

In conclusion, the law subjected to income tax "profit from every work yielding income not subject to another income tax" and does not exempt any income except by express text in the law. Therefore, according to Lebanese law, every work yielding income is subject to income tax, so that no income occurring in Lebanon remains outside the framework of tax imposition.

As a summary of what was mentioned above, Lebanon's adoption of the principle of tax territoriality, or the principle of residence, meaning economic dependence, meaning the place where work is practiced, made every profit or income occurring in the place of work, meaning in the Lebanese geographical scope, subject to Lebanese income tax.

The principle of tax territoriality or adoption of economic dependence is an implementation of Article Three of the Lebanese Income Tax Law, which stated that "tax is imposed in the name of natural and legal persons, residing in Lebanese territory or abroad, on profits they realize in Lebanon."

Based on the mentioned article, it is concluded that consideration is not given to the place of residence of legal, moral, or natural people, but rather consideration is given to the place of profit realization and the place of practicing the activity or effort that led to profit realization.

Therefore, if it is a foreign company but realized profits in Lebanon, these profits are subject to income tax in Lebanon. As for profits occurring outside Lebanon whether persons are residing in Lebanon or outside Lebanon, or Lebanese or foreigners, no tax is imposed on profits or revenues realized abroad resulting from activity they exerted entirely outside Lebanon. Therefore, those subject to tax in Lebanon are either resident taxpayers or non-resident taxpayers, according to the Income Tax Law's definition of the concept of residence.

2.3.2 Implications for Sovereignty

The territorial approach reflects classical sovereignty concepts: the state exercises exclusive fiscal authority within its geographical boundaries. This system functions smoothly in a world where economic activity correlates with physical presence. However, it encounters challenges when other districts assert competing claims based on citizenship (as the United States does) or when economic activity becomes deterritorialized through digital commerce. These challenges are not unique to Lebanon but affect all developing countries with similar tax structures.

3. FATCA: AMERICAN EXTRATERRITORIAL TAX ENFORCEMENT

3.1 Legislative Background and Objectives

FATCA law embodies an encroachment on tax sovereignty, not only in Lebanon but in most countries of the world. States that did not comply with FATCA law were subject to American sanctions, such as Switzerland, France, and even HSBC Bank, in addition to Federal Bank LLC in Cyprus.

An example of this encroachment is the obligation of Lebanese financial, banking, and tax institutions to make tax disclosure about Lebanese holders of American citizenship or residence, or Americans residing in Lebanon or who earn profits in Lebanon, in order to impose American tax on them.

This is the most important dilemma, and this is the subject of deep research in our opinion, which led to reducing the concept of tax sovereignty and led to compromising on it, avoiding and evading consequences greater than not collecting national tax, which is submission to American sanctions.

The Lebanese citizen who holds both Lebanese and American citizenship, and is subject according to Lebanese law to income tax according to the principle of tax territoriality on profit occurring in Lebanon, while according to the American system, it adopted the system of political dependence according to nationality and residence, and must pay tax wherever he realized these profits. The Lebanese state must cooperate with American authorities to help the latter collect its taxes.

Is it permissible for the Lebanese government to favor the American Treasury's interest over its own? Or to detract from its tax rights in favor of American tax rights?

And what concept of sovereignty remains considering these givens?

The American Congress approved the Foreign Account Tax Compliance Act, known as FATCA law, on March 18, 2010, as part of the Hiring Incentives to Restore Employment Act (HIRE). This law came within the tight plan set by the American administration.

The implementing regulations for FATCA law were issued in January 2013.

The Foreign Account Tax Compliance Act (FATCA) is a law issued by the American Congress designed to prevent, avoid, and confront tax evasion by Americans who resort to foreign banking services. FATCA law established a new system to monitor, collect, report, and inform information related to American taxpayers. It was also specifically designed to increase financial abundance and tax revenues to the American Treasury fund.

This law is controversial considering that it was established to be applied on a global scale in all countries and obligates non-American banks and financial institutions to comply with it.

The American Internal Revenue Service (IRS) indicated that the main objective of issuing this law is due to the necessity of imposing American tax rules and laws that require every American citizen to declare all his assets and income wherever he is in the world, and therefore it is a practical mechanism to regulate the tax obligation of American taxpayers.

Under this law, American taxpayers whose foreign financial assets exceed certain limits must disclose those assets to the tax authority.

Since there was an American law obligating Americans to disclose their dealings with foreign banks for considerations related to combating money laundering, the report stipulated in FATCA law is a development of the Financial Report on White Money (FBAR).

It should be noted that the report related to combating money laundering was no longer useful and beneficial for the tax administration to collect taxes on commercial profits of American citizenship holders residing outside the United States of America.

3.2 FATCA's Operational Mechanism

Which financial institutions must comply with this law?

The financial institutions concerned with applying this law are the following:

Deposit-accepting institutions include non-American foreign banks including specialized and commercial banks, lending associations, credit unions, owner unions, building and financing cooperatives, and Islamic financing.

Institutions that have financial assets for others include commercial companies, clearing companies, sister companies, money portfolios, insurance companies, and reinsurance companies.

Institutions operating in investment or reinvestment include mutual investment funds, private equity funds, options, futures, and forward exchange contract funds, venture capital funds, commodity and service management funds, and pension funds.

As for revenues subject to FATCA law provisions, they are as follows: first, interest from deposits and returns from bonds and securities; second, profits resulting from distribution of stock dividends, investment certificates, and investment instruments; third, returns from investment in intellectual property rights; and any other income.

As for financial assets whose revenues are subject to FATCA law, they are the following: bank deposits, financial derivatives contracts, brokerage contracts, insurance and reinsurance contracts, and securities of all types.

However, outside the scope of FATCA law application are real estate investment and revenues resulting from acquisition of antiques, jewelry, gold, cars, real property, and other tangible collectibles as long as they are for personal use.

This phenomenon is among other risks and flagrant violation of local laws in applying FATCA law, which we will address in the second section.

Among what the American Tax Compliance Act includes is that it imposes a tax of thirty percent on the total American-source income paid to non-American financial institutions unless these institutions enter into agreements with the American tax administration and accordingly make every declaration related to American taxpayers who deal with them.

FATCA establishes a withholding-based compliance system. Unless foreign financial institutions enter into agreements with the IRS to identify and report on U.S. account holders, they face thirty percent withholding on U.S.-source payments. This punitive withholding effectively compels global compliance—non-participating institutions risk losing access to U.S. dollar clearing systems and American investment opportunities.

By the end of 2013, the American Foreign Account Tax Compliance Act imposed on all foreign financial institutions to enter into compliance agreements with the American Treasury.

Several studies, including a study by researcher Marsan Dean, indicated the necessity for the global financial system to implement FATCA law requirements, prepare financial reports, and withhold

source tax from all external transactions of American taxpayers in order to combat and fight the phenomenon of tax evasion and achieve tax abundance at the government level.

Noting that the mentioned study encourages cooperation with this law, it overlooked that the mentioned law brings abundance only to the American Treasury. Financial institutions do not need any encouragement because they are obligated by force of imposition and by their submissive and unchosen will to comply with this law, otherwise painful economic sanctions will be imposed on them that may in many cases lead to their collapse.

According to studies conducted by the Union of Arab Banks, amounts potentially collectible for the benefit of the American Treasury Department are estimated at about eight hundred million dollars if thirty percent is deducted from bank accounts in the first year of applying this law, and more than tens of billions if the tax is deducted directly through banks.

Thus, it becomes clear to us how the American legislator wanted to issue a law aimed at imposing its application on all states with their governments and financial institutions, disregarding all legal and sovereign considerations. However, it is easy to issue a certain law, or easier if the expression is permissible, but the more difficult task is finding a mechanism to apply this law. Therefore, applying the American Tax Compliance Act will not be as easy as some researchers might believe or imagine. In our opinion, it is a difficult and complex process and will face many obstacles, difficulties, and even conflicts of interest. This is what we will study in the second paragraph of this section.

3.3 Implementation Models

As for the aspects and mechanism of applying this law, this mechanism embodies tangible examples of exposure and violation of states' sovereignty. As we mentioned above, financial institutions, banks, and governments must conclude agreements with the tax administration in the United States of America to apply FATCA law. Otherwise, if they fail, these financial and banking institutions will be subject to economic sanctions and cessation of dealing with them, which may lead to the deterioration of their business and their fall.

So, what is the mechanism of applying this law?

The provisions of FATCA law are considered extremely difficult and complex. Financial institutions that do not comply with applying this law will find it difficult to work unless they comply and register with the American tax authority. Because if these institutions refuse to comply, American institutions will refuse to continue dealing with unregistered foreign institutions.

The difficulty also lies in the operational scope because it requires finding a mechanism and improving methods of dealing with customers to collect necessary additional data and modify systems to align with applying the American Tax Compliance Act (FATCA).

In 2012, the American Treasury revealed a model for intergovernmental agreements as a mechanism to apply FATCA law. These intergovernmental agreements, according to the Executive Director responsible for FATCA law consultations at Deloitte Middle East, are perhaps the worst option considering that they secure an isolation zone to protect the local banking sector.

According to the first model, governments have a broader role than financial institutions. Priority is given to local legislation through introducing local legislation and implementing it by the executive authority in Lebanon. In this case, foreign financial institutions will not be required to sign bilateral agreements with the American tax administration but only need to register with the American Treasury.

Then financial institutions submit their reports to local governments, and the local authority in turn submits its reports and information in its possession to the American administration.

As for the second model, the role of governments and local authorities is limited. Financial institutions must enter into bilateral agreements with the tax administration and the American Treasury Department. In this case, every financial institution that did not comply with the American Tax Compliance Act FATCA and also refused to lift banking secrecy is reported. Then the local authority reports these reports to the American Treasury Department.

To apply the new American law in Lebanon, Lebanese banks and financial institutions must do the following:

Review customer lists carefully and determine the nationality of each customer and their income sources, search for American shareholders in companies who have no less than ten percent or more.

Request customers wishing to continue dealing with the financial institution to sign a letter lifting banking secrecy in favor of the American tax authority.

Include a clause in account opening contracts and documents indicating the customer's consent to provide information and submit the report between the financial institution and the American tax administration.

Establish new departments to implement this law practically and enhance human resources with the latest mechanisms and technologies and train them to draw the American customer's attention to the importance of compliance so that the bank is not exposed to a fine.

Make necessary amendments to the "Know Your Customer" system.

Between the two models we discussed above, data indicate that recently the total number of countries conducting negotiations with the United States of America and the tax administration has become between fifty and sixty countries. It appears that governments mostly tend not to conclude agreements with the American government.

This means one thing: banks and financial institutions must themselves prepare the mechanisms to be relied upon to apply FATCA law and provide the American tax administration with information related to American taxpayers.

As for Middle East and North Africa governments, these governments are not about to enter into an agreement with the Internal Revenue Service. This means that financial institutions must fully comply with FATCA law requirements.

3.4 FATCA's Impact on Lebanese Sovereignty

As for Lebanon, it appears that it was decided not to adopt the first model that requires entering into agreements at the government level because such a commitment imposes great responsibility that the Lebanese government may not be able, given its modest capabilities, to commit to.

In this regard, Deputy Governor of the Central Bank of Lebanon Mohammad Baasiri considered that it was decided "after long deliberations not to conclude an agreement at the government level regarding FATCA or the American Compliance Act for Foreign Accounts."

So, how will Lebanese financial institutions apply the American Tax Compliance Act?

Practically, the Association of Banks in Lebanon, and it has already started, will conduct negotiations with the American tax authority. It can be concluded from this that the banking association will become the entity concerned with reporting and submitting reports between Lebanese banks and the American tax authority.

On February 7, 2013, the Association of Banks in Lebanon issued an important announcement about applying the American Tax Compliance Act FATCA to all customers of banks operating in Lebanon, explaining the issuance of this law, its content, and the obligations to declare deposits and assets belonging to American taxpayers, and the financial and banking institutions concerned with this law.

The American administration tries to show public opinion that applying FATCA law falls within the framework of international cooperation. However, this law contains many pitfalls and violations of states' laws, and it makes all states hostage to the American administration and its will, so no state dares not to comply with the American Tax Compliance Act.

However, in the context of talking about international cooperation in general, the Central Bank of Lebanon issued Circular No. 126 dated April 5, 2013, whereby it imposed on Lebanese banks and financial institutions to deal with their correspondents abroad according to laws, regulations, procedures, sanctions, and restrictions decided by legitimate international organizations or by sovereign authorities in the countries of these correspondents.

However, it is not permissible in any way, under the title or cover of so-called international cooperation, to violate national sovereignties of local laws and to obligate states to overlook the

application of basic laws or at least make the application of some of their laws a discretionary matter that does not respect at a minimum the principle of equality in applying laws and makes the application of law, which should be characterized by supremacy, subject to discretion and whims of states, and legal rules become a pliable tool in the hands of domination and control policies. What we will examine in the second section of this research will indicate the aspects of violations caused and being caused by the American Tax Compliance Act on Lebanese positive law.

FATCA fundamentally conflicts with Lebanon's territorial tax system. Consider a Lebanese citizen who also holds U.S. citizenship and earns income in Lebanon: Under Lebanese law, this individual owes Lebanese tax on Lebanon-sourced income, implementing territorial sovereignty. Under U.S. law, the same individual owes U.S. tax on worldwide income, including Lebanon-sourced income.

Lebanese financial institutions thus face competing sovereign claims. They must either violate Lebanese banking secrecy laws to report to the IRS or face exclusion from U.S. financial markets—a form of economic coercion that subordinates Lebanese fiscal sovereignty to American tax collection interests.

These requirements impose substantial costs on Lebanese institutions while serving American rather than Lebanese fiscal interests. Studies by the Union of Arab Banks estimated potential U.S. Treasury collections at eight hundred million dollars in the first year of full implementation, with tens of billions projected long-term—revenues extracted from foreign jurisdictions without compensation to source countries or their financial systems.

3.5 FATCA as Tax Imperialism

FATCA exemplifies fiscal imperialism, the powerful state imposing its tax jurisdiction extraterritorially on weaker states that cannot effectively resist. Several factors characterize FATCA as imperialistic rather than cooperative:

First, unilateral imposition where the United States enacted FATCA without negotiation or consent from affected districts. Second, coercive enforcement where the thirty percent withholding penalty functions as economic blackmail. Third, asymmetric burden where foreign institutions bear compliance costs to serve American fiscal interests. Fourth, no reciprocity where despite promises of reciprocal information sharing, the United States has not implemented comparable reporting for

foreign account holders in American institutions. Fifth, violation of legal norms where FATCA compels violations of banking secrecy and privacy laws in numerous districts.

Lebanon, like many developing nations, faces an impossible choice: sacrifice sovereignty and banking secrecy to accommodate American demands, or face economic isolation from global financial markets. The decision to comply represents not cooperation but capitulation—a recognition that fiscal sovereignty means little when confronted with American economic power.

4. DIGITAL ECONOMY TAXATION: THE GAFA CHALLENGE

4.1 The Digital Economy and Tax Sovereignty

On the other hand, FATCA is not the only phenomenon of encroachment on tax sovereignty, or at least conflicts with it. The problem arose of the extent to which imposing electronic commerce taxes and GAFA taxes conflicts with states' tax sovereignty and problems of cross-border internet network extension, where it is difficult to determine the place of tax connection.

Recently, specifically after the spread of coronavirus disease, the volume of electronic commerce increased markedly, and a technological revolution erupted resulting from digital services provided by international companies such as Google, Facebook, and Amazon.

These digital services that appeared in the shadow of traditional tax systems that do not keep pace with the speed of development of digital technology imposed a legal and tax problem, which is how to impose tax on digital products within the framework of electronic commerce system and social media platforms.

This problem is what prompted several countries such as France to search for a new tax model that keeps pace with and suits the development of electronic and digital commerce and considers at the same time states' tax sovereignty due to network globality.

The rise of digital commerce and services creates unprecedented challenges for territorial tax systems. Traditional taxation assumes that value creation occurs in identifiable physical locations—factories, offices, and retail establishments. Digital platforms transcend geography; a company can serve millions of customers in a jurisdiction without any physical presence, making traditional Nexus rules obsolete.

This deterritorialization of economic activity creates what scholars' term "stateless income" "profits that effectively escape taxation due to the inability of source or residence jurisdictions to assert authority. Technology giants like Google, Apple, Facebook, and Amazon exemplify this challenge, operating globally while concentrating intellectual property and reporting profits in low-tax districts.

4.2 Lebanon's Digital Economy Tax Gap

Before detailing the concept of GAFA law, the concept of electronic commerce and its relationship to the tax system must be determined. Electronic commerce means buying and selling operations in the concept of commercial law but relying on social media means or the internet network and covers all commercial transactions that rely on display sites and pages on the virtual network and not in physical stores. This required research into developing tax systems that no longer suit this type of non-traditional commerce to which the traditional tax system applies.

Lebanon's territorial tax system, designed for traditional commerce, struggles with digital transactions. Article 3 of the Income Tax Law taxes "profits realized in Lebanon," but determining where digital service profits are "realized" proves difficult. Is profit realized where the company's servers are located? Where are intellectual property rights registered? Where do engineers develop software? Where do customers access services? Where is payment processed?

A Lebanese consumer purchasing cloud storage from Amazon or advertising on Facebook generates economic value, but Lebanon's territorial system cannot easily capture tax revenue when the service provider has no Lebanese physical presence or legal entity.

From the mentioned definition, the relationship between electronic commerce and the tax system must be extracted. In this regard, we point out that most developing countries that still follow classical or traditional tax laws have not yet faced in the current era reflections on how the growth of electronic commerce affects tax revenue collection. However, the train of international systems is moving at a speed that will force developing countries to join it sooner or later. In this regard, we point to three groups of issues raised by the topic of taxes on electronic commerce.

First, consumption taxes: How to determine the place of consumption for cross-border electronic commerce transactions, and optimal collection and levy mechanisms.

Second, international direct tax issues: Which are represented in the extent of applicability of applying current tax rules to profits of cross-border electronic commercial establishments.

Third, tax administration issues: Which are represented in the extent of applicability of applying current tax rules to profits of cross-border electronic commercial establishments.

Some studies indicated that with the development and spread of electronic commerce in countries' economies, tax administrations began to face challenges accompanying this emerging commercial pattern, pointing to the decrease in government tax revenues with rapid growth of electronic commercial transactions. Governments faced many problems in the process of successfully collecting taxes on these electronic transactions.

Also, the matter settled in legislation in most countries on subjecting foreign entities to tax on business, commerce, and profits occurring within countries, in implementation of the principle of tax sovereignty. However, it was found that because of freedom of movement of production factors and capital supported by information and communication technology, foreign companies deliberately avoid presence and establishing centers in countries that adopt high tax rates. This avoidance would lead to a noticeable decrease in tax revenues of these countries despite the high tax rates in them.

These types of emerging commerce face many difficulties and negatives, most notably: challenging governments in collecting various taxes in effect in the state due to increased utilization of electronic means in the commercial medium; and the international nature of electronic commerce formed an incentive and encouraging factor for tax evasion in light of the inability to inventory and control these revenues and income, especially regarding digital products exchanged via the internet network.

Therefore, the challenges faced by states in this type of commerce can be summarized in the following aspects:

First, nature of products, which were easy to control in the past, so it was easy to control them and impose tax on them, and they were manual, sensory, and tangible, and their change to become intangible, non-sensory, and electronic, which can penetrate borders without tax authorities noticing them.

Second, place of consumption, as the principle is that tax is imposed and collected at the place of consumption, and the principle is that the seller is responsible for collecting value-added tax, but the problem arises if the trader is in one place and the consumer in another place, and this is the essential point raised by electronic commerce regarding indirect taxes on non-digital products.

Third, encroachment on tax sovereignty occurs because of each state's tendency to limit the phenomenon of tax evasion practiced by international electronic commerce, so that each state gives itself the right, power, and authority to impose taxes, leading to tax duplication on a single transaction, which double taxation avoidance agreements are sometimes unable to solve, which would lead to reducing circulation in electronic commerce.

4.3 The GAFA Tax Response

What are GAFA taxes?

GAFA taxes are an abbreviation for taxes imposed on international digital companies, particularly Google, Apple, Facebook, Amazon. This tax was imposed by the European Union in 2018, in the face of strong opposition from the United States of America, which found in the matter an inevitable confrontation to defend its interests since these companies are American companies. Here we tangibly sense how tax imposition has a sovereign character and sovereign conflict and an attempt to control states over others. Among the manifestations of this sovereign conflict is that in March 2018 when the European Union approved the GAFA tax, the opposition from the European Union was since this tax imposed a digital trade war.

Frustrated by revenue losses, the European Union proposed in 2018 a three percent digital services tax on revenues from digital activities including online advertising services, digital intermediation platforms, and sale of user data.

France implemented its own version in 2019, taxing digital companies with over seven hundred fifty million euros in global revenues and twenty-five million euros in French revenues. In a decision issued on Friday, September 12, 2025, the French Supreme Constitutional Court, based on the petition submitted by the German media group Axel Springer, considered that taxes imposed on digital commerce issued in 2019 are constitutional taxes, reinforcing that the mentioned tax did not violate the provisions of equality before the law or public burdens nor even the principle of freedom of commerce, and also that the mentioned tax did not violate any other right or freedom protected by the constitution, and therefore it was acknowledged that the mentioned tax is a constitutional tax.

The GAFA tax represents an alternative sovereignty assertion: rather than waiting for physical presence, source countries tax based on user presence and value extraction from their markets. This approach prioritizes economic substance over legal formalism.

Here we point out that several countries followed behind the European Union and France, especially countries like Uganda, Zambia, and Benin, which enacted laws aimed at imposing tax on the use of social media means, regardless of the purpose of use, whether for electronic commerce or for browsing news and newspapers.

In Mexico, the House of Representatives proposed a bill to impose tax on services provided by digital platforms, by imposing tax on non-resident entities in Mexico for their services provided to persons in Mexico through a digital platform. In our opinion, this proposal comes within the framework of enhancing tax protection and extending tax sovereignty over Mexican territory.

These measures reflect developing countries' recognition that traditional tax principles enable systematic revenue extraction by multinational digital platforms. GAFA taxation represents a reassertion of source-country tax sovereignty adapted to digital economic realities.

4.4 Challenges and Criticisms

Digital economy taxation faces several legitimate criticisms.

First, double taxation risk. When multiple jurisdictions assert taxing authority over the same digital transaction, cumulative tax burdens may exceed total profits. Without comprehensive international coordination, digital commerce faces potential triple or quadruple taxation: corporate income tax in the jurisdiction where profits are legally booked, digital services tax in jurisdictions where users access services, VAT or sales tax on transactions, and withholding taxes on cross-border payments.

Existing double taxation treaties, negotiated for traditional commerce, often fail to resolve conflicts involving digital services.

Second, administrative complexity. Tracking digital transactions across borders for tax purposes raises significant practical challenges including volume where billions of microtransactions occur daily across digital platforms, identification where determining user location for tax purposes requires sophisticated technical mechanisms, privacy where comprehensive transaction

monitoring raises serious privacy concerns, and enforcement where compelling compliance from entities with no physical presence proves difficult.

Third, economic efficiency concerns. Critics argue that digital services taxes may increase consumer costs as companies pass through tax burdens, discourage digital innovation and platform development, create barriers to entry for new digital services, and reduce overall economic welfare by taxing consumer surplus.

4.5 Proposed Solutions

Scholars and policymakers have proposed various approaches to taxing digital commerce.

First, consumption-based taxation. Rather than taxing corporate profits, jurisdictions could impose consumption taxes (VAT/sales tax) collected through internet service providers where ISPs act as collection agents, withholding tax on data transmitted; payment processors where financial intermediaries collect tax at payment point; or platform withholding where digital platforms collect and remit tax on behalf of third-party sellers.

This approach shifts administrative burden to fewer collection points while preserving source-country revenue rights.

Second, bit tax. Some propose taxing data transmission volume—a levy per unit of digital information transferred. Proponents argue this captures previously untaxed economic activity and aligns with benefit theory (using digital infrastructure).

Critics counter that high-value services may involve minimal data transmission, low-value services may involve extensive data transmission, the approach taxes inputs rather than profits, and implementation requires invasive monitoring of data flows.

As for the second proposal, it is applying bit tax that is collected based on the quantity of digital bits used or transferred, and this requires equipment with specific specifications in different devices, starting from the necessity of monitoring wealth that states do not benefit from. Some considered that this proposal is among the best proposals to impose such tax considering that goods are converted into a quantity of bits and their transfer process occurs via the internet, leading to inventorying the actual number of bits transferred and then imposing tax on it.

Several criticisms were directed at this solution, particularly regarding tax duplication, considering that the consumer will pay tax for purchasing the device, and tax for using it to transfer information and electronic goods as well. On the other hand, the claim that this solution will lead to decreased

internet growth and consequent decrease in activities and business. And tracking and monitoring data constitutes an encroachment on privacy and confidentiality. The most prominent criticism is that some goods have very high value relative to bit size, and conversely another service or commodity consists of large bit size, but its value is lower and therefore involves a kind of deception.

Third, significant economic presence. Rather than physical presence, tax nexus could be based on "significant economic presence" indicated by revenue threshold from local users, number of local users or transactions, local advertising or brand presence, and collection and monetization of local user data.

This approach, advocated by international organizations including the OECD, redefines nexus for digital age while preserving source-country taxing rights.

4.6 Implications for Lebanese Sovereignty

In conclusion, unfortunately, there is no choice before Lebanese authorities, like any other developing country, but to deal with this file on the basis of compliance with American laws to avoid sanctions, and not on the basis of protecting Lebanese tax interest and tax sovereignty. This makes us conclude that the concept of tax sovereignty continues to shrink in the face of American tax governance, and from here arose the concept of compliance.

As for encroachment on tax sovereignty through the electronic commerce gateway, some solutions have been devised, particularly imposing tax on consumption instead of imposing tax on productive units, and therefore instead of imposing tax on income, tax is imposed on consumption and property, so that this type of tax contributes to collecting taxes from those evading paying them, considering that some achievement of these revenues they spend.

However, this theory can be strongly criticized because it leads to obligating non-evaders of paying tax to bear additional tax resulting from evaders' mistakes. Another idea emerged through imposing this tax on the consumer through companies providing internet service, so that the company distributing the internet plays the role of intermediary between the government and consumers.

However, this theory was also criticized since tracking customers' electronic transactions raises issues related to customer confidentiality on one hand, and security issues on the other hand may lead to increased burdens on consumers, leading to slowing the growth of electronic commerce.

Lebanon has not yet implemented comprehensive digital economy taxation, though the Ministry of Finance has studied various proposals. The digital tax gap represents a sovereignty challenge distinct from but related to FATCA. With FATCA, a foreign government extraterritorially asserts tax authority over Lebanon-sourced income. With the digital gap, foreign companies avoid Lebanese tax authority despite extracting value from Lebanese users.

Both phenomena erode Lebanese fiscal sovereignty and state capacity. Digital taxation presents an opportunity for Lebanon to reassert source-country taxing rights, but implementation requires legislative action by amending tax law to establish digital nexus standards, administrative capacity by developing systems to identify, track, and tax digital transactions, international coordination by negotiating to prevent double taxation while preserving Lebanese revenue rights, and technical infrastructure by building capabilities to monitor and enforce digital tax obligations.

The stakes extend beyond revenue. Effective digital economy taxation demonstrates fiscal sovereignty and state capacity—the ability to adapt legal frameworks to economic realities and assert authority over value extraction from national territory and population.

5. COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS: SOVEREIGNTY UNDER PRESSURE

5.1 Asymmetric Power Relations

Both FATCA and digital economy taxation reflect asymmetric power relationships in international tax governance.

FATCA represents powerful-state imperialism: The United States leverages its economic power to impose extraterritorial tax obligations, effectively subordinating other nations' sovereignty to American fiscal interests. Developing countries like Lebanon must comply or face economic isolation.

Digital economy taxation represents developing-country resistance: Source countries attempt to assert taxing rights over economic value extracted by multinational technology firms, most based in developed countries. The European Union, representing collective economic power, led this resistance, enabling smaller nations to follow.

5.2 Erosion of Traditional Sovereignty Concepts

Classical Westphalian sovereignty assumed territorial exclusivity—each state exercised authority within its borders without external interference. Modern international tax reality deviates fundamentally.

First, there are overlapping jurisdictions where multiple states claim legitimate authority over the same income. Second, extraterritorial enforcement where states compel action by institutions in other jurisdictions. Third, economic coercion where powerful states use market access as leverage for compliance. Fourth, privatization of enforcement where private institutions such as banks and platforms become tax collectors for foreign governments.

5.3 The Concept of Tax Sovereignty in Practice

For developing countries like Lebanon, tax sovereignty increasingly represents an aspiration rather than reality. Practical sovereignty requires not just legal authority but capacity for enforcement and resistance to external pressure. Lebanon possesses legal sovereignty—domestic law grants

exclusive taxing authority over Lebanon-sourced income—but lacks practical sovereignty to resist American demands or effectively tax digital commerce.

This gap between legal and practical sovereignty characterizes much of contemporary international relations. Formal equality of states coexists with profound inequality in capacity to assert and defend sovereign prerogatives.

6. CONCLUSION AND POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS

6.1 Key Findings

It is evident from the above that some states adopted mechanisms and legislation to impose tax on electronic commerce and tax on social media platforms in what is known as GAFAs taxes. Among the problems resulting from applying these laws, mechanisms, and legislation are problems related to tax justice, tax duplication, and state tax sovereignty. It remains that the positive aspect is that as much as technology provided many mechanisms for taxpayers for tax evasion, digitization also provided many opportunities for tax administrations to limit tax evasion through information provided by technology, which allows controlling taxpayers' income, especially in light of the trend towards electronic payment.

This study demonstrates that traditional concepts of tax sovereignty face unprecedented challenges from two directions: powerful states asserting extraterritorial jurisdiction (exemplified by FATCA) and economic activity deterritorialized through digital technology (exemplified by GAFAs taxation debates).

Lebanon's territorial tax system, predicated on exclusive jurisdiction over Lebanon-sourced income, proves inadequate to address these challenges. FATCA forces Lebanese institutions to serve American tax enforcement, effectively creating dual sovereignty over income earned within Lebanese territory. Digital commerce enables systematic extraction of economic value without taxation under Lebanese law.

These challenges reflect broader transformations in international political economy. First, power asymmetry where developing countries lack capacity to resist fiscal imperialism by powerful states. Second, economic transformation where value creation increasingly occurs through intangible, deterritorialized digital activities. Third, governance gaps where international tax law, designed for physical commerce, fails to address digital economic realities. Fourth, enforcement asymmetry where powerful states and multinational corporations can exploit legal arbitrage while developing countries cannot.

6.2 Policy Recommendations for Lebanon

For short-term adaptations, first, FATCA compliance optimization. While unable to resist FATCA, Lebanon should minimize compliance costs through centralized government-level coordination rather than institution-by-institution implementation, negotiating IGA terms that protect Lebanese institutions from conflicting legal obligations, and ensuring reciprocal information exchange—if Lebanon shares data with the U.S., it should receive equivalent information about Lebanese assets in American institutions.

Second, digital economy tax legislation. Enact comprehensive digital services tax based on significant economic presence thresholds adapted to Lebanese market size, revenue-based rather than profit-based taxation to prevent base erosion, and collection mechanisms through payment processors and ISPs.

Third, administrative capacity building. Invest in tax authority capabilities including digital transaction monitoring systems, international tax expertise and training, and cooperation agreements with other developing countries facing similar challenges.

For long-term strategic initiatives, first, regional coordination. Lebanon should engage with other Arab states and developing countries to share best practices for digital economy taxation, present unified positions in international tax forums, and negotiate collectively with powerful states and technology companies.

Second, international advocacy. Support multilateral efforts to establish equitable international tax rules that respect source-country rights, combat fiscal imperialism through international legal frameworks, and ensure developing country participation in global tax governance.

Third, legal framework modernization. Comprehensively revise Lebanese tax law to define nexus standards for digital economy, establish transfer pricing rules preventing profit shifting, and create legal mechanisms for information exchange that preserve Lebanese sovereignty.

6.3 Theoretical Implications

This study contributes to scholarly understanding of sovereignty in the contemporary international system. Tax sovereignty proves neither absolute nor indivisible—it exists on a continuum determined by power relationships and state capacity.

For international tax scholarship, the Lebanese case demonstrates that first, territorial taxation remains vulnerable where physical presence nexus rules cannot effectively tax deterritorialized digital commerce. Second, compliance costs constitute sovereignty costs where when developing countries must implement foreign tax regimes, they bear financial burdens while surrendering fiscal autonomy. Third, sovereignty requires capacity where legal authority means little without enforcement mechanisms and ability to resist external pressure.

6.4 Future Research Directions

Further research should examine first, comparative experiences of how other developing countries managed tensions between FATCA compliance and fiscal sovereignty. Second, economic impacts include the revenue effects and economic consequences of digital economy taxation in developing countries. Third, alternative frameworks such as blockchain technology or other innovations enable new approaches to cross-border tax administration that preserve sovereignty. Fourth, legal evolution of how international law might evolve to balance legitimate tax enforcement with respect for sovereignty.

6.5 Concluding Observations

Tax sovereignty remains fundamental to state capacity and autonomy. Revenue collection finances public goods, enables redistributive policies, and demonstrates governmental authority. Erosion of tax sovereignty correspondingly undermines state capacity across all dimensions.

Lebanon faces difficult choices with no easy answers. FATCA compliance subordinates' Lebanese fiscal interests to American revenue collection but non-compliance risks economic isolation. Digital economy taxation could reclaim revenue currently lost to multinational platforms but risks double taxation conflicts and administrative burdens.

These dilemmas reflect Lebanon's position as a small developing country in an international system dominated by powerful states and multinational corporations. While this study identifies

challenges and proposes policy responses, fundamental solutions require transformation of international tax governance to respect sovereignty and equitable revenue distribution.

Until such transformation occurs, Lebanese policymakers must navigate between inadequate options, seeking to minimize sovereignty costs while preserving essential fiscal capacity. The perfect should not become the enemy of the good—pragmatic adaptations that reduce harm deserve support even when they cannot fully resolve underlying structural inequalities.

REFERENCES

- Baasiri, M. (2013, April 25). Lecture on FATCA law. Al-Liwa Newspaper. Beirut, Lebanon.
- Cosnard, D., & Piquard, A. (2025, September 12). French Constitutional Council upholds the GAFA tax. *Le Monde*. Retrieved from https://www.lemonde.fr/en/politics/article/2025/09/12/french-constitutional-council-upholds-gafa-tax_6745338_5.html
- Dean, M. (2010, September). The global financial system must now implement a new U.S. reporting and withholding system for Foreign Account Tax Compliance, which will create significant new exposures: Managing the risk. *Taxes*.
- Ibrahim, N. A. (2012, December). Analytical study of accounting and tax effects resulting from applying the American Foreign Account Tax Compliance Act on financial institutions (Field study). Cairo, Egypt.
- Internal Revenue Service. (n.d.). Foreign Account Tax Compliance Act (FATCA). Retrieved October 30, 2025, from <https://www.irs.gov/>
- Internal Revenue Service. (n.d.). Report of Foreign Bank and Financial Accounts (FBAR). Retrieved October 30, 2025, from <https://www.irs.gov/>
- Kashkoul, S. A. (2017). The impact of electronic commerce on tax imposition. *Journal of Economic and Administrative Sciences*, Baghdad, Iraq, 470.
- Legislative Decree No. 144. (1959, June 12). Income Tax Law. Lebanese Republic.
- Melikaoui, M. (2021). Electronic commerce taxes and GAFA taxes between states' tax sovereignty demands and network extension problems: Study of some international trends. *Journal of Tax Studies*, 10(2), 105-119.
- Al-Mifraji, A. H. (2007). Electronic administration. Arab Organization for Administrative Development. Cairo, Egypt.
- Ministry of Finance, Lebanon. (2002, December 18). Circular No. 2541/S1 on the application of Article 46 of Legislative Decree No. 144.

Ministry of Finance, Lebanon. (2013, April 5). Circular No. 126 on foreign correspondent compliance.

Mohammed, A. Z. A. (2014). Tax organization of electronic commerce and proposals for adoption in Palestinian reality (master's thesis). Al-Najah National University, Palestine.

Othman, S. A., & Al-Ashmawi, S. R. (2007). Tax economics: Policies, systems, and contemporary tax issues. University House. Alexandria, Egypt.

Out-Law.com. (n.d.). Foreign Account Tax Compliance Act (FATCA). Retrieved October 30, 2025, from <http://www.out-law.com/en/sectors/financial-services1/banks/foreign-account-tax-compliance-act-fatca/>

Saleh, A. (2006). The tax system in Lebanon: Taxes and fees (1st ed.). Sader Legal Publications. Beirut, Lebanon.

Salman, J. N. (2018, October 24). Types of tax systems globally. Retrieved from www.nedalshabi.ps

Tarbieh, J. (2012, October 4). Seminar on FATCA law. An-Nahar Newspaper. Beirut, Lebanon.

The Association of Banks in Lebanon. (2013, February 7). Announcement to all customers of banks operating in Lebanon. Retrieved from <http://www.abl.org.lb/ar/NewsDetails.aspx?pageid=1538>

U.S. Congress. (2010). Hiring Incentives to Restore Employment (HIRE) Act, Pub. L. No.